

SYSTEMATIC STUDIES ON THE RELATION BETWEEN INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Four levels of surface treatment were performed on carbon fiber. Surface properties on carbon fibers were measured such as surface oxygen content. 0 and 90 degree tensile tests were carried out with unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates, and also mode I interlaminar and intralaminar fracture toughness tests were conducted with the CFRP laminates. The relation between the surface properties and the mechanical properties of the CFRP laminates was cleared in this paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interfacial properties have been important in composite materials because it is often encountered the composite materials can not achieve required properties such as high strength, modulus, water resistance, etc., although fiber and/or matrix possess high properties.

Particularly in carbon fiber reinforced plastics, the relation between interfacial properties and adhesive mechanisms have not been cleared. Carbon fibers were subjected to anodic acid oxidation method, carbon fiber maker officially have not opened. Surface treatment on the fibers is great know-how for the fabricating company, however, these attitudes are obstacle of development of composite materials, so that composite industries were led to dark age.

The purpose of our series investigations for carbon fiber reinforced composites is to understand relation between interfacial properties including chemical analysis and composite materials properties such as general properties and crack propagation behavior. In our papers, we described the detail of surface treatment; that is amount of electric charge and type of acid solution. Surface analysis was performed by using X-ray photoelectron microscopy (XPS) and mechanical properties of treated fibers were also measured. Mechanical properties of unidirectional CFRP laminates were evaluated through tensile tests (0 and 90 degree) and mode I fracture toughness tests. In the case of mode I fracture toughness tests, both interlaminar and intralaminar tests were carried out.

2. MATERIALS

Four levels of surface treatment were carried out on PAN based carbon fiber (AT-400: Asahi chemical Industry Co.,Ltd.,) by varying amount of electricity through 8% nitric acid aqueous solution by anodic oxidation method. These carbon fibers are designated as CF1 to CF4. Surface oxygen content and acid function on carbon fiber was measured by XPS and neutralization titration. Fig.1 shows the relation between the surface oxygen content, the acid function and amount of electricity of four kinds of carbon fiber used in this investigation. Both O1S/C1S and acid function linearly increased with increasing amount of electricity.

Fig.1 Relation between surface oxygen content, acid function and quantity of electricity.

3. FIBER PROPERTIES

Properties of the four kinds of carbon fiber used in this study are listed in Table 1. Specific surface area of each carbon fiber is changed with varying amount of electricity, so that physical adhesion properties were also changed. On the other hand, tensile modulus, tensile strength and ultimate strain were independent of amount of electricity. These results expect that longitudinal properties of CFRP laminates will not be changed.

Table 1 Carbon fiber properties.

	Electricity (coulomb/g)	Surface area (cm ² /g)	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Ultimate Strain (%)
CF1	0	0.601	4.39	238	1.82
CF2	7.23	0.541	4.42	241	1.83
CF3	10.94	0.584	4.39	237	1.82
CF4	15.37	0.557	4.41	239	1.81

4. TENSILE TESTS

Four kinds of carbon / epoxy prepregs with different surface treatment levels were manufactured by using an industrial prepreg manufacturing plant. Unidirectional CFRP laminates were molded in an autoclave. Laminates for 0 degree tensile tests were 1.2mm thick, and that for 90 degree tensile tests were 3mm thick. Fig.2 shows tensile specimen geometry. Tensile tests were carried out with stroke rate of 1.3mm/min. by using Instron 4507 universal testing machine.

Tensile properties for 0 and 90 degree CFRP laminates were summarized in Table 2. Fig.3 shows the relation between tensile properties for both 0 and 90 degree and O_{1s}/C_{1s}, where (a) shows tensile modulus and (b) shows tensile strength. Tensile modulus for both 0 and 90 degree CFRP laminates were independent of surface properties of carbon fiber. On the other hand, tensile strength for 0 degree CFRP laminates was independent of the surface properties, but tensile strength for 90 degree CFRP laminates greatly depended on the surface properties. The 90 degree tensile strength for CF4 specimens increased by about 103% over that for CF1 specimens.

Fig.2 Tensile specimen geometry; (a) 0 degree and (b) 90 degree.

Table 2 Tensile properties of 0 and 90 degree CFRP laminates.

	0 degree		90 degree	
	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
CF1	133	2020	7.1	35.3
CF2	139	2260	7.2	55.5
CF3	130	2010	7.0	69.0
CF4	140	1960	7.3	71.6

Fig.3 Relation between (a) tensile modulus, (b) tensile strength and O1S/C1S.

5. MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

Mode I interlamimar fracture toughness tests were carried out by using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen as shown in Fig.4. Initial defects were introduced into specimens by inserting 6µm thick aramid film with release agent during molding the laminates. The fracture toughness tests were carried out under stroke control by using Instron 4206 universal testing machine. Initiation values of the fracture toughness was calculated from the point of maximum load in the initial load-displacement curves. The calculation method of the fracture toughness was followed by JIS K7086.

The relation between the initiation values of mode I interlamimar fracture toughness (interlamimar-GIC) and O1S/C1S) are shown in Fig.5. The interlamimar-GIC of each specimens was almost constant without respect to O1S/C1S.

The surface of carbon fiber on fracture surface was observed by using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). SEM micrographs of the fiber surface on the fracture surface were shown in Fig.6. The carbon fiber surface was exposed and small debris of resin adhered on the fiber surface in the case of CF1 specimen. On the other hand, in the case of CF4 specimen the fiber surface was almost covered with resin and almost of all grooves on exposed fiber surface was covered with resin. In spite of these differences of fracture surface, interlaminar-GIC was independent of the surface properties on carbon fiber. This means that mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests may be not convenient for evaluating methods of fiber / matrix interface of unidirectional composites.

Fig.4 DCB specimen geometry.

Fig.5 Relation between interlaminar-GIC, intralaminar-GIC and O1S/C1S.

Fig.6 SEM micrographs of interlaminar fracture surface for (a) CF1, (b) CF2, (c) CF3 and (d) CF4 specimens.

6. MODE I INTRALAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

Mode I intralaminar fracture toughness tests were carried out by using special DCB specimen whose width direction was set to the thickness direction of laminates as shown in Fig.7. Initial defects were introduced by saw cutting of the width of 0.3mm, which was followed by special fine edge file finishing. The radius of notch root was about 50 μ m. The fracture toughness tests were conducted under stroke control by using Instron 4206 universal testing machine. Initiation values of the fracture toughness was calculated from the point of maximum load in the initial load-displacement curves. The calculation method of the fracture toughness was followed by JIS K7086.

Fig.7 Special-DCB specimen geometry.

FE-SEM

epoxy A

Fig.8 SEM micrographs of intralaminar fracture surface for (a) CF1, (b) CF2, (c) CF3 and (d) CF4 specimens.

The relation between the initiation values of mode I intralaminar fracture toughness (intralaminar-GIC) and O1S/C1S are shown in Fig.5. The intralaminar-GIC increased with increasing O1S/C1S. The rate of increase for CF4 specimen was about 56% over CF1 specimen.

SEM micrographs of the fiber surface on the fracture surface are shown in Fig.8. Bare fibers were observed on the intralaminar fracture surface, and the diameter of the bare fibers was equal to the fiber diameter without respect to O1S/C1S. However the amount of resin adhered in grooves on fiber surface was different between them. Much more resin was observed in the grooves on carbon fiber in the case of CF4 than in CF1.

7. DISCUSSION

0 degree tensile properties were independent of surface properties on carbon fiber, because the four kinds of carbon fibers treated with different surface treatment displayed almost same tensile modulus and tensile strength without respect to the surface properties. However 90 degree tensile strength greatly depended on the surface oxygen content.

On the other hand, in the case of mode I fracture toughness, interlaminar-GIC was independent of the surface properties and intralaminar-GIC depended on the surface oxygen content. On the bases of fractographic observation, schematic models of crack growth mechanism were proposed in Fig.9. In the case of interlaminar tests (Fig.9(a)), the crack grew through the interface region near by fiber surface in CF1 specimen and resin rich layer between plies in CF4 specimen. Thus, the crack path moved from the interface region to the resin region with increasing O1S/C1S. On the other hand, cracks run through the same fiber bundle for intralaminar tests (Fig.9(b)) without respect to O1S/C1S. The crack propagated through the interface region regardless of O1S/C1S. That is reason why the mode I interlaminar-GIC was independent of O1S/C1S and mode I intralaminar-GIC increased with increasing O1S/C1S.

(a) Interlaminar mode I

(b) Intralaminar mode I

Fig.9 Schematic diagram of crack growth mechanism for (a) interlaminar and (b) intralaminar tests.

Fig.10 shows the relation between 90 degree tensile strength and intralaminar-GIC of each CFRP laminates with different surface treatment. In only the case of 90 degree tensile tests and intralaminar fracture toughness tests, the CF4 specimen displayed higher tensile strength and fracture toughness, respectively, than the CF1 specimen.

In summarize, it can be noted that 90 degree tensile tests and mode I intralaminar fracture toughness are convenient as the evaluation method of the fiber / matrix interface. The CF4 specimen displayed good interface in this work.

Fig.10 Relation between intralaminar-GIC and 90 degree tensile strength.

8. CONCLUSIONS

- 1.Surface oxygen content on carbon fiber increased with increasing amount of electricity.
- 2.Tensile strength for 0 degree CFRP laminates was independent of surface oxygen content, but that for 90 degree CFRP laminates increased with increasing surface oxygen content.
- 3.The initial values of the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates was independent of surface oxygen content. On the other hand initial values of mode I intralaminar fracture toughness increased with the increase of surface oxygen content.
- 4.Amount of resin adhered in grooves on carbon fiber surfaces in both the interlaminar and intralaminar fracture surface increased with increasing surface oxygen content.

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